

MYSTERY OF NAVAMSHA

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Abstract:

Sage Varahmihir's Hora Shastra was compiled on a scientific basis approximately 2000 years ago. Several researchers have developed this and efforts have been made to bring it closer in accuracy in astrology from the prediction point of view. In predictive astrology, initially, the Rasi, forming one-twelfth part of the ecliptic, was the only basis used. As it was found insufficient, Nakshatra 13⁰.20' concept came in to use as the prime factor of Hora Shastra. Later the Nakshatra pada of 3⁰.20' was incorporated by researchers since critical analysis failed by using Nakshatra 13⁰.20', which matches the span of Navamsha. Different divisional methods (vargas) like Hora, Drekkana, etc up to ten such division were developed by many brilliant researchers, which is part of the development of Hora Shastra. South Indian astrologers declared that Navamsha method is the most realistic and closest in delineation amongst all the divisional charts, after thousands of experiments with divisional charts. Because of their firm faith in the Navamsha system, the South Indian astrologers are in the forefront. This paper also examines the importance of Navamsha chart and hidden facts of our life.

Key Words: Nakshatra, Pada, Zodiac, Rasi, Lagna, Natal Chart, Planets, Navamsha, Vargottam, Puskaramsa, Longitudes, Aspects, Malefic, Benefic, Exalted, Debilitated, Compust, Retrogate

The Magnificent View:

Navamsha operates on the planetary longitudes along the ecliptic. Normally, any operation through scientific methods purifies, strengthens and multiplies the normal effects of the matter under consideration. Navamsha position is attained by multiplying the natal planetary positions nine times. In this process, small things are seen under a powerful microscope, bringing reality to light and thereby gauging its internal developments; hence its secrets are exposed.

An example of the longitudes of ascendant, the Sun and Jupiter in a chart:

The Sun	03 ⁰ .00'	Taurus
Jupiter	13 ⁰ .00'	Libra
Ascendant	16 ⁰ .20'	Taurus

When asked to talk about prestige and success, one would not be comfortable to predict much due to many interlinking malefic aspects in the chart. But by operating through Navamsha we get different longitudes as under:

Ascendants & Planets	Longitude in Natal Chart	Navamsha Pada	Placement in Navamsha
Ascendant	16 ⁰ .20' in Taurus	5 th	27 ⁰ in Taurus vargottam, trine to Sun & Jupiter
Sun	30 ⁰ .00' in Taurus	1 st	27 ⁰ in Capricorn, combust to Jupiter and trine to Ascendant
Jupiter	13 ⁰ .00' in Capricorn	4 th	27 ⁰ in Capricorn, combust to Sun and trine to Ascendant

From the above placement in the Navamsha one feels confident to give a more positive picture due to Sun combust Jupiter and both these planets are trine to the ascendant from the 9th house. The vague and indistinct prediction in the natal chart, becomes clear in the Navamsha chart. The Navamsha chart becomes very important in delineating complicated horoscopes. Hence, the Navamsha chart is supreme among other divisional charts.

Soul and Last Birth:

We can understand our soul and last birth karmas from this small story. There was a very wild gangster who has been a killer and he is a person of total anti-law. This gangster kills people and steel money from them and he involve in all sort of things against the law.

One day while running from the police this man had a leg slip and thrown into a flowing river. The river takes him down stream and police tried to find him but they are not able to locate where he is.

As a twist of destiny this man reaches were a group of monks living in that place. These monks took him out of the water and gave treatment to his legs which got fractured and his head is severely injured and it took around a month to heal back from his injuries. But unfortunately this gangster loses his memory and starts to think that he is one among the monks. He starts to live a very beautiful life like getting up early, doing meditation, chanting mantras and having very sathvik meals.

Everything about him is very nice. Within a year he becomes as very good monk. People started following him because as he is a very good and intelligent in his behaviour. In one fine morning, the police identified the gangster and arrested him.

They put him in the jail. But this monk is pleading to understand that he is not a gangster, but a monk. This is what happens with every soul who is born on this earth. Everybody thinks that they have done nothing wrong to deserve all this and everybody is a monk, everybody is saadhu, we are doing good things but bad things happen to us. This is the story about every soul.

To understand the journey of the soul this navamsha is important. Technically speaking navamsha is 1/9th part of a sign and a sign is about 30 degrees and navamsha is about 3°20'. This navamsha by the vedic astrology is the sum of our past birth. It could be ten births, it could be one birth but it gives you the average of our good, bad, and ugly karmas of our last birth, until our last birth. That is why in vedic astrology, the way in which masters see first the navamsha chart, then the moon chart and then our lagna chart. The lagna chart has a very less importance compare to other charts, let say navamsha or moon chart because of this is this birth only.

The basic understanding of navamsha is, if a planet is strong in navamsha that means that the karma pertaining to those relatives planet what you suppose to do all things in positive manner. If a planet is weak in navamsha it implies that you will not get good results because of this planet despite that planet is being very strong in the main chart. This is the basic rule of navamsha. So people are misunderstanding these days and try to do remedies for navamsha.

Karmas We Have Already Done:

There is an election in our state / country. We go and cast our votes what we decided.

We give our votes to a particular candidate and that candidate probably wins and he becomes the Chief Minister/Prime Minister of the State/country. The results are declared and everything is sealed. But now we approach the authorities and say that I think I casted a wrong vote, I want to change my vote. Is it possible? It is not possible. Because result has been declared and everything taken care of and sealed and people are won and they are sitting where they are elected. This is the 2nd part of navamsha.

What karmas we have done we cannot undo them. We are looking for remedies. Lot of people are looking for remedies for navamsha but the ballot is already been cast and it is impossible now. People say Saturn is strong in navamsha so I wear a blue colour dress because it is strong in navamsha. It is not going to make a yoga in difference. The ballot has been cast and the candidate has won or lost, that thing is being sealed and you cannot change the navamsha. For the journey of the soul in this birth navamsha is the starting point like you have a race of 500 metres in a big stadium but you cannot find all the candidates are standing in the front position.

They must run in circle, the inner circle is small, the outer circle is very big. So in this birth we find some people standing in ahead of us. We mistake them that they will be the winners in the birth but we do not realise that they are standing there because their circle is very big, they have to run faster than us, longer than us, he is the one man behind everybody is the last one and he may do very well in this world but being the last one he have the smallest circle to run that he will achieve quickly if he put his more efforts. This is the entire picture of Navamsha.

To summarise it, navamsha is the sum total of all our karmas, good, bad, an ugly from our past birth. It is the starting focal point of our journey of our soul from this birth. So, we put the navamsha first. Planet stronger in navamsha, weaker in the main chart still will give good results. Because you have a plus for that planet, you done very well for that planet. However planet weak in navamsha, stronger in main chart may not give you very good results. An exalted planet in the D9 chart means you done some very good karmas for that particular relative, peoples, friends whatever was supposed to be given to that planet you given the at most and the best but in the end, you did something that you will have to return for that particular planet and that's why an exalted planet in the navamsha is debilitated in this birth. But still you will have very good excellent results. The problem is not this. The problem is that you have a debilitated or a weak in the navamsha and the soul has ask God, give me a chance and I will improve my relationship with all the souls related to that particular planet. For planets weak in the navamsha you have to put lot of hard work because we have been given few births or janmas to correct the relationship with those persons. It is been found that people who have a weak planet in the navamsha generally tent to overlook the relatives in this birth also regarding those planets. Let us say your Venus is debilitated in the navamsha it is mandatory that you need to maintain a good marriage in this birth, it is mandatory because the soul has asked a chance that I will clear my debts with this particular human being or

to this particular soul. However the flip side is more dangerous. Where the planet Venus is very strong in the navamsha and you do not respect the partner in this birth. Your strength generated throughout the years will get last in this birth, because it is the blessings of that soul you are here in the particular place in the navamsha. Stronger Venus leads good, luxurious life, good reputation, you do not have lot of hindrance in the life, you eat the best, live in the best places, ride best car, have a lot money jewellery everything. It is penance of life. Other examples are, when a planet is varkottam (varkottam means same sign in the navamsha and same sign in the main chart). This is the stronger combination to have. Why a stronger combination, because the soul has decided that he will take this planet up-ward from his last birth and he will still take the upwards in this birth. Here debilitation can also mean strength.

Your Mercury debilitated in the navamsha and your Mercury debilitated in the main chart, you are on the upward journey of mercury. People who are debilitated Mercury in varkottam are very intelligent people because mercury has to do with intellect. The soul has decided, it is ok fine, it will use his intellect positively, please bless me with that. But still my navamsha is debilitated I did not use my intellect properly and in greatest of purity in my last birth. So the people have been given a chance that is why it is said in the vedic system the navamsha is the top, the moon chart second and even if you don't show your lagna chart doesn't make it difference. There is no need to see the lagna chart, because your sun is strong in D9 you will definitely be in fond of government and get favour from government, to get a high position, you will be associated with people in power, you yourself will get name, fame, money everything. Now in this birth you maybe ruin something probably think too much of your destiny and put in things to wrong and go against the law and caught or do something bad, spoil your own name and integrity but you are blessed with the strong planets. That is why it is important to focus on the navamsha first.

When you see a chart, first see the navamsha to know about the journey of the soul. That is the starting point of this running race where this person is standing in a bigger circle or smaller circle at what speed, is he a good runner or really dwell up running in this birth. Then see moon chart, moon chart is very important because it passes down the strength of the navamsha through your mind. The mind is manasu but not a logical part but manasu, with sastras talk about this. Vedic astrology treats a human body or human form in three types. The first is the soul, then the mind is mum and the body. For them the body is the last. The journey of this soul is first, that means that navamsha is prime for them, then the mun, the emotional mind with the compilation of the intellectual mind. The moon chart and then the lagna chart finally that is this birth. People achieved in business, family business and their horoscope says that person is going to ruin, lot of politicians having getting good backing they ruined alliance with other things. It is all about the navamsha. The starting point is very strong, you started with very good family background, good big politician family but you could not hold that act because probably the moon chart was very weak. They were not as strong as their predecessors to understand the integrity of business, the integrity of politics. It takes a lot of intelligence to carry forward any burden. Some body from a very huge sophisticated business family must keep up the name is very big burden. You and me are the luckiest people, we have no bag and baggages. We just have to prove ourselves in this birth. But we do not carry anything big from there. Oh! My God, we know the business tricone of so and so, or the son of so and so or the daughter of so and so, a lot of things are expected from our people. Start navamsha like this. Whenever people talk about remedies from navamsha now we can understand that why they will not work. They will work at least your desire. Because you are trying to change something that is already been casted - the ballot is being cast and someone elected, Govt has been formed, nothing can be done on that. It is highly logical to understand this point. You have a weak planet in this birth but it is very strong in the last birth. Wear a stone or do the remedies for this on that way suggested by astrologers. But people will cry that they doing remedies for more than five years and it is not been helping them. No remedies for navamsha. Remedies only for either the moon chart where a planet is strongly influencing the moon and the moon is accepting that strength. This is the reason why in vedic astrology the name must be put with that particular letter or alphabet where your moon sign or the nakshatra rises in which part which exactly you have to pronounce your name from the first letter from that word. Its keeps on giving strength resonate more strength to the moon. So the scientific reason is even if we born with a weak moon some body keeps repeating that name is going to bring more strength to mind. We have a bridge here. We have the navamsha which may be weak, we have lagna chart which may be very weak but we may have moon that is being blessed by our mother the lord of our moon so that we can sail through this birth easily despite a weak navamsha and a weak main chart. The first point where the sastras says that we need the blessing of our mother even if God does not bless you. So we have to understand the scientific version of navamsha why remedies donot work out from navamsha.

Now coming out to understand deeply about this navamsha. The first part in navamsha is its lagna. Whatever lagna rises in our navamsha it should be friendly to this birth lagna chart, so that lagna of navamsha should be friendly to lagna of this birth. If there is 6-8-12 relationship you have a struggle full life. If the navamsha is varkottam, the same lagna for navamsha and as well as in lagna chart, is one of the excellent combinations to have. A planet strong in the navamsha, weak in the main chart will trouble you, why because it wants you to keep generating the strength. But it will not give a very malefic results, because it is strong in the

navamsha. You can bank upon that planet to give luck you needed. Reverse is not true. A planet weak in the navamsha and strong in the main chart denotes that by permission of the Almighty you ask that he will strengthen his relationship with this particular planets and the souls which are in the form of relatives in this birth. Any weaker planet in the navamsha identify the relatives related to that, identify the karmas related to that planets and do them multifidly, even if the people don't treat you decently and in dignified manner, because they do not owe anything to you but you owe lot of karmas to them, satisfy planets weak in the navamsha. A planet neutral there, neutral here is the same but the lagna is very important. Lagna of navamsha is going to define the strength of this birth chart.

Chandra Kala Nadi:

According to "Chandra Kala Nadi" the position and status of the planets in the Navamsha to be reckoned from the ascendant of the Rasi Chart. The planets during their dasha period will bestow the results of the Amsha to which they have moved in the Navamsha Chart. Each divisional chart has a Karaka Planet. For Navamsha, the main Karaka Planet is Venus for both male and female chart. Mars and Jupiter can also be considered. The position of Moon in the Navamsha Chart is also important. In transit, when Saturn transits over this moon sign, the native may have to undergo difficulties pertaining to the domain of Navamsha.

Navamsha Tulya Rasi and Rasi Tulya Navamsha:

Corresponding to the treatise "Chandra Kala Nadi" the concept of Navamsha Tulya Rasi and Rasi Tulya Navamsha have been propounded. This means that the Rasi Chart is super imposed on the Navamsha Chart and the analysis is done. If two planets join in the same Navamsha it is termed as "Navamsha Sama Yoga". The 64th Navamsha has great importance and any slow moving planets like Saturn, Jupiter, Ketu while transiting this point denote important events in the life of a native. The benefic indicates favour and the malefic indicates unfavourable events. We must see whether the Lord of Navamsha in which moon is placed is having what kind of relation with the 64th Navamsha while judging longevity of the native.

If Rahu transits the 64th Navamsha, death of a near relative may be anticipated, but if Saturn transits, the death of native may be predicted. The native born in Vargothama Amsha will be talented and will have leadership qualities.

Jaimini System:

As per Jaimini System the planet with higher degree is called "Atmakaraka" and the sign of placement in the Navamsha is called "Karakamsha". We can use this Karakamsha for predicting the profession of the native.

Sarvashtaga Varga:

From the Sarvashtaga varga, the number of bindus of a planet are high in both rasi and Navamsha charts very good results will be expected, vice versa the native may slip to a lower level in life. The dasha of the planets positioned in such houses, bad effects may be predicted.

Deva, Nara and Rakshasa Navamshas:

By dividing the Navamsha into three parts, we get a set of three Navamsha named as Deva, Nara and Rakshasa Navamshas. It is very useful in marriage predictions.

Dhuruva Nadi:

Dhuruva Nadi and Chandra kala Nadi will help to study the navamsha planets with respect to the Rasi Chart.

Navamsha Tulya Rasi Gochara:

If any planet transits a sign in which moon or other planets are positioned in the Navamsha Chart the results can be predicted and this is called "Navamsha Tulya Rasi Gochara. Chandra kala Nadi gives the detailed explanation of the role of dispositor of Navamsha Chart.

Navamsha:

Navamsha is 1/9th division of a sign of 3° 20' that is equal to 1/4th part of a nakshatra. The whole world 12 zodiac signs with 27 nakshatras is divided into 108 parts.

Sequence of counting Navamsha:

The counting starts from the cardinal sign of each element.

- For Fiery signs : count from Aries
- For Earthy signs : count from Capricorn
- For Airy signs : count from Libra
- For Watery signs : count from Cancer

Vargottam:

A planet occupying the same sign in the natal (D1) and Navamsha (D9) chart is known as vargottam. A vargottam planet is thought to be very powerful, auspicious, and capable of its main and sub-dasha periods and transits.

The parts of the sign of vargottam are:

- 0° 00' to 3° 20' – Aries, Cancer, Libra, Capricorn – Movable – First Part
- 13° 20' to 16° 40' - Taurus, Leo, Scorpio, Aquarius – Fixed – Fifth part

- 26°.40' to 30°.00' - Gemini, Virgo, Sagittarius, Pisces – Dual sign – Ninth part.

House	Vedic Name	Characteristics
1	Tanu Bhava	Personality, Physique, Overall life
2	Dhana Bhava	Wealth, Family, Food, Speech
3	Sahaja Bhava	Co-borns, Courage, Valour
4	Sukha Bhava	Happiness, Mother, Vehicles, Land, Domestic environment
5	Putra Bhava	Children, Past life, Creativity, Romance
6	Ari Bhava	Disease, Enemy, Resistance power, Competition
7	Kalatra Bhava	Marriage, Spouse, Partnerships
8	Aayur Bhava	Longevity, Inheritance, Type of death
9	Baghya Bhava	Dharma, Luck, Father, Religion
10	Karma Bhava	Profession, Activity, Power, Livelihood
11	Labha Bhava	Gains, Fame, Elder brother
12	Vyaya Bhava	Expenditure, Foreign visit, Spirituality, Moksha

Barbara Pijan Lama on Navamsha – the fruits of Dharma:

- Fruits of Dharma - All divisional charts depict the "fruits," "attainments," or "results" of life's fundamental pursuits
- The bhava that forms a 3/11 angle to bhava - 10th represents the goals, attainments, or "fruits" of any matter.
- 11th from bhava 10th shows How the goal is defined
- 3rd from bhava 10th demonstrates the native's courage in achieving that goal.
- The house in the 3/11 position from the subject matter can tell us whether a goal is properly set and properly energised to manifest.

Navamsha is the “fruits” of Dharma:

- The "fruits of dharma" are represented by the 11th from the 9th - radix bhava - 7.
- As a result, one's marriage and the spouse who creates the marriage with us are significant fruits of one's dharma.
- Because the 9th house is the "seed" that produces the "fruition" of marriage, we must understand the psycho-dynamics of the 9th house in order to understand the spouse and the marriage.
- Internal marriage interactions - clearly defined in the divisional - 9th-house, "Navamsha"

D9 = Field of Psychic Expectation for Matters of:

- Maintaining good relation with neighbourhoods.
- The Divine Presence is manifested through the partner based on the behaviour between the human relationship.
- Fruits (11) of Faith (9) - The life experience of the human beings based on the presence of divine providence.
- Navamsha represents the private, intimate seeds that create community and that can be seen as a fruit = marriage.

Vargottam's Effects:

If the native's Sun, Moon, Ascendant, and Ascendant Lord tends to fall in the vargottam, by becoming famous or the leader of his group, he will achieve a respectable high social status. It is unlucky, if Vargottam does not fall in the last division of a sign. If it is Vargottam, he will be virtuous, famous, modest, and the social leader. Vargottamsha graha is commonly found in the radix and Navamsha.

Satya:-

Charamabhavaneshvaadhyamshaa: stireshumadhyadvimurthyshu Thathaanthya: I
 Vargothamaa: prdhishtaastesh viha jaathaa: kule mukhya:II
 (Chapter 3 of C.S. Patel's Navamsha in Astrology)

Vargottam Navamshas are:

- The 1st Navamshas in movable signs namely Chara.
- The 5th Navamshas in fixed signs namely sthira.
- The 9th Navamshas in mutable signs namely dviswabavi.

The person born in these rising Navamshas are in the highest in their family.

Jatakparijate Chapter – 1 verse: 34

Chare chadhya shako ne ya:
 stire madhyanavaam shaka:
 antyaamshako dviswabhave iti smruta:

Vargottam is when a planet occupies same sign in Navamsha which was occupied by it in birth chart.

Yavanene:

Yavanene – sve sve graheshu shakaaya Saste

munibhirukta:

The vargottam rising Navamsha or Vargottam planet indicates that its Rasi and Navamsha dispositor are the same planet.

An example of the impact of such a variable:

In D1 and D9, Mars - Dhanushu = vargottam.

The effects are:

- During (transit) travel of Guru over Sagittarius (conjunct Mars)
- or enters Aries sign (trine)
- or enters Gemini sign (opposition or mutual dristi)
- or enters Leo sign (again trine)

Both the native and the spouse will have the opportunity to either accelerate or slow their progress.

When the native enters a Mars period, the effects of Mars-Dhanushu will be felt not only by the native, but also by the spouse.

A Vargottam Ascendant Makes the Natal Chart Very Strong.

Lagnachandrika – P.45-46 verses 93, 94, 95.

Subhavargottame janma vyayastane cha sadgrahe I

Asunyeshu kendreNu karakaakyagraheshu cha II (93)

Suryekendre Rajasevee vaisha vrittirnishakare I

Sasravritti: kuje shuro bhude chaadhyaapako bhaveth II (94)

Swaanushtaana ratho nityam divyabuddhir naro gurau I

Sukre vidhyartha sampanno neechase vee saanaischare II (95)

Karaka Planets Occupying a Kendra	Indications
1. The Sun	Public Servant
2. The Moon	Entrepreneur
3. Mars	Police or Military man
4. Mercury	Teaching Profession
5. Jupiter	Religiously related activities
6. Venus	Luxury & Wealthy
7. Saturn	Helping poor people

Brihat Yavan Jatak – Page 328, Verse 47:

A person with all 7 grahas in Vargottam Navamsha. He would be a great and strong ruler, subduing his opponents and endowed with super elephants whose ichor drops will moisten the earth

The Udith Navamshas:

If the Navamsha Lagna - vargottam and the owner of house (Lord) is placed in good sign place in the birth chart, or if the said Navamsha will be strengthened due to benefic in the D9 chart, the person will be joyful until the rest of his life.

Vargottam Planets Bestowing their Results

(Book by C.S. Patel's Navamsha in Astrology)

Planets	Results Bestowed
The Sun	Ideological mindset, Strong minded, good health, social status, fame, motivation to learn, and identity
The Moon	Sound mind, wisdom, strong and neutral mindset, and the capacity to achieve the best output.
Mars	Astrology Knowledge, motivation, denoting the reason for life's ups and downs
Mercury	Strong mind, ability to persuade others, Kind in speech, and Astrology Knowledge
Jupiter	Clever, Good Health, quest for honesty, ability to understand others' perspectives, and dignity
Venus	Ability to understand the pros and cons of a problem, physical growth, and astrological knowledge

D-9 Lagna & owner (Athipathi)

Basic Attitude towards Marriage:

- When the owner of the D9 lagna, which represents the person's own behaviour in relationship, lies in the dusthamsha (6, 8,12), marriage suffers.
- (Buddha-ruled) = envious and openly warlike, with the possibility of chronic animosity.
- 8 (Kuja-ruled) = secretive and devious, with the possibility of catastrophic upheaval.
- 12 (Guru-ruled) = not conflicted but on the verge of becoming disconnected Spiritual concerns disintegrate marriage energy. When the owner of D9 rules the radix lagna, the person's behaviour takes centre stage in the marriage.

- Spouse-partner must frequently "leave it or take it," with some power to compromise to settle or change.

Navamsha and the Soulmate:

- A soulmate is an etheric personality. It has no inherent material value. Several individuals find that their soulmate(s) stay mainly in the etheric or causal realm.
- Navamsha illustrates the identity of one's partner(s), with whom the individual has agreed to partner up in order to enhance one's spiritual growth prior to the current birth.
- "Marriage is not a long date," Dr. Phil Mark says. It is a collaborative effort. Partnerships necessitate both give and take, as well as compromise." Because one's premise of "partner in life" could indeed intelligent into outward manifestations of decided to commit partnership, with all the self-importance and material difficulty that long-term loyalty involves, one will discover that one's Navamsha offers an immensely accurate view of one's "partner in life."

Indications of the 12 Houses of the Navamsha Chart when the Bhavas and their Lords are Strong and well Accepted:

Houses	Indications
1	Marriage is strongly suggested by a strong Navamsha lagna and lagna lord.
2	Shows the spouse's longevity, wealth, and skill.
3	It provides the considerable strength to keep the marriage going.
4	It demonstrates marital fulfilment and true happiness
5	With intelligence, one can avoid an unpleasant situation.
6	A powerful and well-regarded 6th house triumphs over relationship issues and challenges in life.
7	A strong and well-aspected 7th house provides a caring and excellent life partner.
8	Accidents, unexpected events, and extramarital affairs are all dealt with by this house.
9	It addresses the spiritual aspects of marriage. If afflicted by the Lords of the Sixth, Eighth, and Twelfth Houses, it takes away the true meaning of faith and belief in matrimony.
10	A benefic 10th house provides propitious rituals, and one observes his marital duties.
11	If the spouse is aggravated, he or she will have unquenchable worldly desires.
12	Sexual fulfilment, outgoings, restraint, partnering demise, and so on.

Assurance and denial of Marriage:

- If the lagna, 2nd house and 7th house are well accepted and strong then there is an assurance of marriage for the native.
- When the above three houses and their lords have malefic aspects and afflictions then the marriage will be denied or delayed considerably.
- Venus well-placed and of dignity in the natal and Navamsha charts assures marriage.
- When the lagna and 7th house and their lords are afflicted in 2, 6, 8 and 12 houses in the natal and Navamsha charts, then marriage will be denied.

Multiple Marriages:

- The lagna lord should be strong in the natal and Navamsha charts-either exalted, in own sign or well-placed in kendras, trikonas or eleventh house.
- The 7th house should be afflicted or have malefic association
- Presence of dhana yoga gives multiple marriage
- Placement of 2nd, 7th and 12th lords in upachaya houses (Houses 3,6,10 and 11).

Upachaya Houses and their Indications:

- The third house - place of courage and confidence.
- The sixth house - place for enemies, perseverance and work related issues.
- The tenth house - for profession, career, promotions in career, challenges faced and how one overcome that effectively
- The eleventh house - place for friends, benefits through income, the peak of a person's desires.
- The third house and the eleventh house are part of Kaama Trikona – Kaama means desires.
- The sixth house and tenth house are a part of Artha Trikona – Artha means security (financial security)

Pushkar Navamsha:

Pushkar Navamsha are twenty four. Each sign has two Pushkar Navamsha and are the special areas of a sign. Any planet placed in this area it will get enhanced qualities and acquire the potential to give good results of its significations. These are the benefic Navamsha and are lorded by the benefics in Navamsha. Any planet occupying this Navamsha goes to the signs of four benefics Jupiter, Venus, Mercury, and Moon. Among 24 Pushkar Navamsha, 18 falls in Jupiter & Venus, 6 falls in Moon & Mercury and no Pushkar Navamsha falls in the sign of Sun, Mars & Saturn in D9.

Tables for Pushkar Navamsha:

Signs	Navamsha	Degree	Sign in Navamsha
Aries. Leo. Sagittarius	7 th , 9 th	20°00' - 23°20' 26°40' - 30°00'	Libra, Sagittarius
Taurus, Virgo, Capricorn	3 rd , 5 th	6°40' - 10°40' 13°20' - 16°40'	Pisces, Taurus
Gemini. Libra. Aquarius	6 th , 8 th	16°40' - 20°00' 23°20' - 26°40'	Pisces, Taurus
Cancer, Scorpio. Pisces	1 st , 3 rd	0°00' - 03°20' 06°40' - 10°00'	Cancer, Virgo

*Source: Book on “Predict with Navamsha, V. P. Goel”

Nakshatra of Jupiter and Sun contain six Pushkar Navamsha each out of total twelve Navamsha. Nakshatra of Venus, Moon, Rahu, and Saturn contribute three Pushkar Navamsha each. The Nakshatra of Ketu, Mercury and Mars do not contain any Pushkar Navamsha. Only three Navamsha are Vargottam and Pushkar at the same time. These are fifth in Taurus, first in Cancer and ninth in Sagittarius.

Placement in Pushkar Navamsha enhances the significations of the planet. For example Jupiter is the significator of wealth. When Jupiter is in Pushkar Navamsha and the sign occupied by Jupiter in Navamsha falls in Kendra or Trikona of the birth chart then the person is very wealthy and lucky. In case, this sign is in sixth, eighth or twelfth, then along with wealth, it gives disease, bereavement, or separation (Chandra kala nadi). Thus the planet acquires the goodness and acts through the house occupied by its Navamsha in the birth chart. Planets in Pushkar Navamsha are benefic and produce favorable results in Muhurat, Horary also.

Some rules for application of Pushkar Navamsha are given:

- Dasha of planets in Pushkar Navamsha is favourable and give results of the house of its placement.
- Planets aspected by planets in Pushkar Navamsha also give favourable results.
- More planets in Pushkar Navamsha lift the level of horoscope.
- Placement of Pushkar Navamsha planet in Navamsha is of maximum importance.

Example Chart to Understand the Application of Pushkar Navamsha:

Birth Chart of Shri M.G. Ramachandran			
Lagna Chart			
	Jupiter		Ketu
Asc	M.G. Ramachandran		(Saturn)
	POB : Kandy		
	DOB : 17.01.1917		
Mars©	TOB : 09.15.00		
	Time Zone 5.30		
(Mercury)©	Latitude : 07 N 18		
Sun	Longitude: 80 E 39		
Raghu		Moon	
Venus			

Planetary Position:

Plantes	C	D	Rasi	Longitude	Nakshatra	Pada	Relation
Asc			Aquarius	17.41.18	Satabhisa	4	
Sun			Capricorn	03.47.30	Uttara Ashada	3	Enemy
Moon			Libra	11.45.01	Swati	2	Neutral
Mars	*C		Capricorn	13.17.32	Sravana	1	Exalted
Mercury	*C	*R	Capricorn	08.33.29	Uttara Ashada	4	Neutral
Jupiter			Aries	03.57.18	Ahswini	2	Friendly
Venus			Sagittarius	09.26.16	Mula	3	Neutral
Saturn		*R	Cancer	04.36.55	Pushya	1	Enemy
Raghu		*R	Sagittarius	26.48.39	Uttara Ashada	1	
Ketu		*R	Gemini	26.48.39	Punarvasu	3	

Note: *C – Combust, *R – Retrograde

Vimshottari Dasha:

Balance of Dasha: Raghu 11 Y1 M 20D

Dasha	Period	
	From	To
Raghu	17.01.1917	07.03.1928

Jupiter	07.03.1928	07.03.1944
Saturn	07.03.1944	07.03.1963
Mercury	07.03.1963	07.03.1980
Ketu	07.03.1980	07.03.1987
Venus	07.03.1987	07.03.2007
Sun	07.03.2007	07.03.2013
Moon	07.03.2013	07.03.2023
Mars	07.03.2023	07.03.2030

Vargottam:

Planets	Sign in Lagna Chart	Sign in Navamsha Chart
Ketu	Gemini	Gemini
Raghu	Sagittarius	Sagittarius

Pushkar Navamsha:

S.No	Planet	Nakshatra	Pada	Lord of Nakshatra	Sign in Navamsha	Lord of Navamsha Sign
1	Raghu	Uttara Ashada	1	Sun	Sagittarius	Jupiter
2	Mercury	Uttara Ashada	4	Sun	Pisces	Jupiter

Two planets occupy Pushkar Navamsha in this horoscope. They also influence other planets.

- Mercury is in Capricorn in third Navamsha.
- Raghu is in Sagittarius in ninth Navamsha.
- The Lord of eleventh house (Sagittarius) Jupiter is aspecting his own house where in Puskar Navamsha Raghu is sitting.
- Mercury aspect Saturn.
- Raghu and Ketu are Vargottam.
- Four planets are related to Pushkar Navamsha and two are in Vargottam.
- Dasha of Saturn lasted till 1963. After that Dasha of Mercury started on 07.03.1963 and lasted till 2004.
- In Saturn Dasha he became a member of State Legislative Council in 1962.
- In Mercury Dasha he was first elected to the Tamil Nadu State Assembly. He became the Treasurer of DMK party in 1969.
- In Mercury Dasha he became Chief Minister of Tamil Nadu on 30th July, 1977.
- He was the first cine actor who became the Chief Minister of State.
- Still he was known as “Makkal Thilagam”, “Ponmana Selvar”, “Puratchi Thalaivar”, “Idhaiya Deivam” etc.,
- He is still alive in the heart of many people in Tamil Nadu.

Conclusion:

The "Fruits of Dharma" are Navamsha. The fruits of dharma are represented by the 11th from 9th = radix bhava-7. As a result, one's marriage, and the spouse who creates the marriage with us, is a major fruit of one's dharma. Because the 9th house is the "seed" that produces the "fruition" of marriage, we need to understand the psycho-dynamics of the 9th house in order to understand the spouse and the marriage. The divisional 9th house, "Navamsha," clearly defines the internal interactions of marriage. There are still many mysteries in Navamsha, and I will discuss the remaining mysteries in my next article.

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